

ARCTIC PASSION

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Education & Training Plan

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9 – Connecting the pan-AOSS with society through communication, dissemination and engagement

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1 – AWI-APECS

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Executive summary

The empowerment through education and capacity building of the next generation is a key aspect of Arctic PASSION. This Arctic PASSION Education and Training Plan conceptualises the education and training formats planned for the next four years: The Arctic PASSION School with two corresponding online workshops, and an online seminar and dialogue series. Arctic PASSION intends to reach out to the next generation impacted by the changing Arctic environment and applies the co-creational aspect of the whole project to the education activities. Key aspects such as the co-development and exchange of knowledge, inclusion and dialogue of different people, perspectives, career levels and backgrounds crosscut over all formats. The planned activities are mainly targeted to Indigenous and non-Indigenous early career scientists, as well as Arctic and Indigenous Youth. This plan also outlines their involvement in the Arctic PASSION project, by acting as Arctic PASSION Ambassadors and as representatives in the Arctic PASSION Consortium.

Introduction and purpose

Arctic PASSION stands for 'Pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems (pan-AOSS): Implementing observations for societal needs'. The project aims at creating a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system, suitable for end-users' needs and co-created together with local and Indigenous Communities. Further information about the project is available at www.arcticpassion.eu.

To reach the main objective, various types of interactions between Arctic PASSION partners, rights holders and stakeholders and target groups are essential. The strategies and plans for these interactions are specified in four interrelated documents: the Communication Plan, Dissemination & Utilisation Plan, Stakeholder Engagement Plan and Education & Training Plan. This document focuses on education and training. Please refer to the abbreviations list in the Communication plan.

Arctic PASSION intends to reach out to the next generation impacted by the changing Arctic environment (school graduates, graduate students, PhD candidates). The next generation will pursue the project's aims even after the project has ended and the pan-AOSS has been implemented. At that point, the monitoring and observing of the Arctic changes shall be sustainably continued. Thus, the empowerment through education and capacity building of the next generation is a key aspect of Arctic PASSION.

As the whole concept of Arctic PASSION is based on the co-creation of knowledge (see the Arctic PASSION Stakeholder Engagement Plan for the definition of co-creation), the project's education and training strategy is also based on interactive learning formats and two-way communication by offering an in-person training school with two interactive online workshops and an online dialogue series. These formats will increase the interaction of different generations, audiences and sectors. Beside learning from each other and exchanging knowledge, it is also about connecting people, listening and sharing experiences. Thus, capacity building efforts in Work Package 9 will bring Arctic PASSION an important step closer to overcoming (mental) barriers to approach different kinds of groups and to learn about different perspectives.

The main target groups for the education and training activities are Indigenous and non-Indigenous early career researchers working in the Arctic Regions and Arctic and Indigenous youth. As far as possible, for all activities Arctic PASSION attempts to ensure gender balance and diversity in the composition of both, trainers and trainees.

To ensure the involvement of early career researchers and their perspectives on Arctic PASSION throughout the whole project's duration, one early career researcher will have a position in the Advisory Board.

Arctic PASSION training school with two online workshops

The Arctic PASSION School is a multi-day training focussing on Arctic observing systems and societal needs in the Arctic. The school is embedded into a sequence of two online workshops (see below). As a result of this training programme the participants will become Arctic PASSION Ambassadors, disseminating the message to different target groups and staying closely involved in the Arctic PASSION consortium by bringing in their perspectives. The current title “training school” is considered as a working title and will be evaluated later in the process.

The specified **target group** for the Arctic PASSION School are Indigenous and non-Indigenous early career polar scientists (graduate students, PhD students) from all over the world working in the Arctic Regions and Arctic and Indigenous youth. Seats will be reserved for early career scientists of the Arctic PASSION project and specific efforts will be made to recruit Indigenous participants.

To completely align and catch up with the next generation’s ways of modern communication and zeitgeisty educational tools, Arctic PASSION will initially make an **online survey** with the specified target group. In this way, Arctic PASSION can learn about the expectations, visions and wishes on Arctic observing systems: What kind of Arctic PASSION topics are of interest? What can we learn and deepen our understanding? Which format of teaching and learning seems most suitable? How are best learning outcomes achieved? Which Arctic location provides the best learning outcome? With this call for input sent to the Indigenous and non-Indigenous early career scientists and Arctic and Indigenous youth, Arctic PASSION applies the co-creational aspect of the whole project to the education activities. The survey will be published via the websites of Arctic PASSION and the Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) and social media channels, the channels of youth-led associations of the Arctic. Additionally, the internal early career researchers of Arctic PASSION will be asked at the Arctic PASSION General Assembly in March 2022 to provide feedback on relevant education and training activities and there will be the opportunity to engage in these activities (e.g., early career network of Arctic PASSION).

After the evaluation of the survey, an in-person multi-day training **school** for approximately 20 early career scientists and Arctic and Indigenous youth based on the wishes and conceptions from this audience will be organised. Before participation, each Arctic PASSION School participant will produce one-minute short videos, so-called FrostBytes, explaining their scientific/educational/personal background to be published on the APECS and Arctic PASSION websites. **FrostByte** videos are a living resource demonstrating the diversity of polar research and an effective science communication tool. For Arctic PASSION, trainers and trainees will learn about their backgrounds prior to the training activity and the videos will be a legacy for Arctic PASSION Work Package 9 activities.

In case the global situation is not permitting in-person meetings or global vaccines are still unequally available, the school could be redesigned into an online or hybrid training. However, active in-person exchange and sharing is strongly preferred as participants are more focused and motivated when experiencing all kinds of input with all senses and can build networks more easily, personally and sustainably.

Figure 1: Concept of the Arctic PASSION training program. The early career scientists and Arctic and Indigenous youth become involved early in the process and get the opportunity to co-develop the training formats aligning to their needs. In the 1st Workshop the participants of the Arctic PASSION School will be introduced to the Arctic PASSION project. The Arctic PASSION School is the main element of the Arctic PASSION training offers. The 2nd Workshop will have the same audience, however the listeners (school participants) will become speakers, giving feedback on the project and bringing in their perspectives and ideas. For one year after the school, the school participants will stay involved with the project as Arctic PASSION Ambassadors. They will have their own outreach projects to disseminate the message of Arctic PASSION to a selected audience in their selected format. More detailed information on the concept see below.

Depending on the survey's results, the **schedule** will include a variety of lectures, discussion rounds, excursions and networking events. The school will be attended and led by leading scientists and project partners, end-users of the pilot services, stakeholders and Indigenous rights- and knowledge holders (see the Arctic PASSION Stakeholder Engagement Plan for the definition of the different stakeholders) as speakers and mentors. The mentors will accompany and initiate discussion rounds, share experiences and mingle with participants. In the selection of trainers and trainees Arctic PASSION will ensure gender balance and diversity. The participants will be able to interactively discuss all different spheres of the pan-AOSS in Arctic PASSION, the Copernicus Services and the eight Pilot Services (Work Package 4) with the mentors. These topics will all be discussed with a special emphasis on exchange with Indigenous Knowledge holders. The key concept of this school is the two-way learning regime, as the school participants and leaders will learn from each other's perspectives and knowledge in open discussion rounds.

After completing the school, Arctic PASSION will maintain the involvement of the school participants during the project as they will become "**Arctic PASSION Ambassadors**". They will have their own Ambassador project to disseminate lessons learned beyond the group of end-users, rights holders and stakeholders and to increase the reach of the in-person-training. Arctic PASSION Ambassadors act as multipliers and share their newly gained knowledge through outreach products or projects with a wider audience of their choice. The project will be chosen and developed by each participant and could be of any format, whether it is a blog, a publication, a presentation or activities with schools. It is also conceivable that the ambassador project is realized as a social media campaign throughout the school days by being in charge of postings on the happenings, topics and discussions during the course and to open up for further discussions online e.g., with other Arctic and Indigenous youth and early career scientists who cannot attend the in-person meeting and to create a more open, inclusive and accessible school for everybody.

Location plays an important role for the focus of the training school. The location will be evaluated closely and potentially at a study site of one of the Arctic PASSION Pilot Studies (see Work Package 4). The advantage of a Work Package 4 pilot study location is that participants will be

provided insights to the ongoing work of the pilot studies and close engagement in rights holder and stakeholder dialogues. The aim is that they can grasp the bigger picture of the environmental and societal situation on site together with all partners involved, including the challenges and opportunities of the communities.

At the end of the training school, participants will be asked to formulate their personal key message in two short **statements** as a video or written message. Firstly, these Arctic voices can comment on the thematic framework of the co-creation of the pan-AOSS for societal needs, its challenges, opportunities and other kinds of visions or wishes. The statements will be put together into one video and will be published on the Arctic PASSION and APECS communication channels (website, social media). Secondly, Arctic and Indigenous youth and early career researchers can share a message to the Arctic PASSION consortium as a means of providing input, ideas, feedback and criticism. The second statement will be internally disseminated through the Arctic PASSION community and incorporated into the project's further progress.

Networking is an important aspect of the school. During the school there is room for networking on professional and casual occasions, which hopefully provides the basis for a sustainable network. There are possibilities to continue working together and having an active exchange within the group.

After the school, various **outputs** and platforms (digital, paper, press, conferences, other in-person meetings) such as online seminars, educational materials, suggestions for improvements, etc. will be published and be available for all audiences. Where possible, information will be disseminated in the major local and/or Indigenous languages.

The Arctic PASSION education and training activities will be coordinated with other training activities of EU Polar Cluster projects to maximize impact and ensure collaboration in the cluster.

In summary, the school will support international exchange and the multidisciplinary education of early career scientists and Arctic and Indigenous youth. The Arctic PASSION School enables interactive discussions that result in the dissemination of the project's intentions and, ideally, in the formulation of recommendations for future cross-cutting initiatives in Arctic observing. These will be communicated widely to the research community, rights holders and stakeholders, decision-makers and end-users.

Online workshops for Arctic and Indigenous youth and early career researchers

The Arctic PASSION School is complemented by two 2-hour-online workshops framing the topics covered during the school. The aim of these workshops is to make the content available to a broader Arctic and Indigenous youth and early career researcher audience (other applicants and additional interested Arctic and Indigenous youth and early career researchers) than the defined group of school participants. Besides Arctic PASSION School participants, a group of Arctic PASSION members (person involved in the pilot services, person involved in rights holder and stakeholder dialogues, data scientist, natural scientist, project manager, etc.) will attend the online workshops.

The **first online workshop** will take place after the Arctic PASSION School participants have been selected and before the school starts. The workshop will introduce the Arctic PASSION

project, its goals and the current updates. A diverse group of Arctic PASSION members and additional cooperation partners (end-users of pilot services, Indigenous community members, Arctic PASSION collaborators, policy-maker, etc.) are invited to attend and some will report from their work, experiences and visions in Arctic PASSION. Beside the input of the project during the workshop, the participants can get to know each other and the Arctic PASSION members before all meet personally at the training school.

The **second online workshop**, after the training school, is a recap and presentation of learning outcomes, and includes the sharing of stories and experiences (content-wise and from rights holder and stakeholder interactions). The participants of the post-school workshop will be similar to the group as before but now switch roles. Speakers of the pre-school workshop will now be listeners. After these speakers opened their plans and aims in the first workshop, it is now time to listen, learn and interact with the participants. School participants will present and discuss their ideas, suggestions and recommendations for the Arctic PASSION project. It is a dialogue forum to give the Arctic PASSION Ambassadors an opportunity to speak to the project members. After the workshop, the feedback, input and recommendations etc. from the participants will be reviewed in a rolling review process to finally reassess the project's actions. In order to do this, the two online workshops can be recorded for internal use, if there is consensus.

For further networking and social interaction, an informal online gathering will be organised (e.g., Gather Town). Support will be provided for further networking activities to promote discussions and pursue engagement and motivation for this topic and to further guide the way of Arctic PASSION from a next generation's perspective. The ambassadors will stay closely involved with the Arctic PASSION project as they will be added to the Arctic PASSION mailing list for 'externals' (see Arctic PASSION Communication Plan), if they agree. Ideally, an Arctic PASSION early career network is established and persists through the duration of the project by giving advice and input, and is potentially sustained beyond that time period.

Preliminary timeline

January 2023	Announcement and lecture plan to be posted on the APECS and Arctic PASSION website and an announcement call send out (see Milestone 9.1 in Month 30)
February 2023	Application Deadline for Arctic PASSION School
March 2023	Review of applications
July 2023	Workshop 1: Introduction from Arctic PASSION internals to early career researchers and Arctic and Indigenous youth
August 2023	In-person multi-day Arctic PASSION School
September 2023	Workshop 2: Recap, Recommendations from early career researchers and Arctic and Indigenous youth, and Dialogue with Arctic PASSION internals
July 2024	Report on the Arctic PASSION School (see Deliverable 9.3 in Month 35)

Online seminar and dialogue series

A series of online dialogues and seminars will present the themes of Arctic PASSION and relevant topics to build capacity within and beyond the Arctic PASSION community and inflame a more inclusive and proactive dialogue with people from different groups, backgrounds and career levels. The video conferences vary between a seminar and a proactive dialogue character depending on the topic. Dialogues are based on the interactive participation of participants, e.g., in breakout rooms, which maximises exchange of different perspectives even in online formats and promotes the meeting and discussion of people from different fields who would otherwise not come together at one table.

The seminars and dialogues are mainly targeted at Indigenous and non-indigenous early career researchers (school graduates, graduate students and PhD candidates) and Arctic and Indigenous youth. The Arctic PASSION project with e.g. project partners or end-users of the pilot services as speakers, benefits from the dialogue discussions as take-home messages from the dialogues will be reported to the Steering Group and further evaluated for the project's progress.

The first run of the series will be an introductory online seminar on the Arctic PASSION project with the project management office team (Work Package 10). A part of the online seminars will be co-developed with Work Package 4 (closely with the Arctic PASSION partner Snowchange) to document the eight Pilot Services with a special emphasis on Indigenous and Local Knowledge and to discuss applications for respective end-users. APECS Project Groups¹ (e.g., the Indigenous Collaborations Group or the Science & Diplomacy Group) will also provide valuable input and support.

Projects and further related, relevant topics for the Dialogue Series are:

- Introduction to Arctic PASSION
- Microplastics in Finnish Lapland
- Permafrost thaw in Siberia
- Fire risk in Canada, Alaska and Siberia
- Life in the Arctic: An exchange between early career scientists and Arctic and Indigenous youth
- Changes in the Arctic: An exchange between Saami and Arctic PASSION scientists
- Storytelling and media training (see Arctic PASSION Communication Plan)
- Science Communication (e.g., how to collect outreach material in the field?)
- Gender-related differences in observing and monitoring of change
- Science diplomacy
- Rights holder and stakeholder engagement

¹ <https://www.apecs.is/who-we-are/project-groups.html>

The composition of moderators and speakers will be diverse, intersectoral and international. Early career scientists and Arctic and Indigenous youth are not only the audience but will also be presenters, moderators and interactive panellists. Where possible bi-directional, bottom-up approaches will be adopted, such as using pro-active dialogue and participatory tools like surveys during the online seminars.

The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists is the main organiser and develops the strategy of the Online Dialogue Series that will take place regularly throughout the project duration, approximately every 3-5 months. The timing of the seminars depends on the topicalities of the project's themes and availability of presenters, participants and audience groups. Announcements of upcoming online seminars will be advertised with a reference to the specific target group, in the APECS community (website, newsletter, social media), Arctic PASSION community (website, social media and newsletter), in networks and organisations (e.g., youth-led associations, EU Polar Cluster) and it will be sent out to appropriate target groups via email or other direct communication channels. APECS will provide the Zoom platform for all online dialogues. Zoom is a globally well-known software for teleconferencing and distance education and is accessible even at remote locations in the Arctic. All recorded dialogues and seminars will be made available open-access on the APECS and Arctic PASSION websites and associated video channels (e.g., APECS Vimeo channel) beyond the project's duration. The Arctic PASSION website will include a separate section for early career researchers and Arctic and Indigenous youth, to collect the outputs from workshops, dialogues and the Ambassador projects.

In summary, the online dialogue series will connect people and promote exchange between intersectional groups. The goal is to build capacity, spark interest and create an active exchange between different generations and sectors. The input from the online seminars and dialogues broadens experience horizons and builds capacity in interdisciplinary thinking and the frame of Arctic observing systems and its related topics. Especially, the involvement of the next generation and learning from their perspectives is of high value for the project and will be considered in the further strategic development of Arctic PASSION.

Preliminary timeline

The Online Dialogue Series will be organised in accordance with current occurring topics of relevance and new results within the duration of Arctic PASSION.

January/February 2022	Introduction to Arctic PASSION and the Pilot Services
March 2022	Storytelling workshop and media training for early career scientists
April 2022	Online Dialogue on Microplastics in Finnish Lapland

Implementation of the plan

This plan lays out the basis and concept for the Arctic PASSION education and training activities over the next four years.

The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists has the main responsibility to facilitate the described formats, the Arctic PASSION school with two corresponding online workshops and the Online Seminar and Dialogue Series, and will further develop those within the next months.